

***Parsleya* nomen novum: a replacement name for the preoccupied *Kailidiscus* Zhao, Sumrall, Parsley et Peng, 2010 (Echinodermata: Edrioasteroidea)**

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Abstract: This paper introduces *Parsleya* nomen novum, a replacement name for the preoccupied *Kailidiscus* Zhao, Sumrall, Parsley et Peng, 2010.

Keywords: echinoderm, homonymy, ichnofossil, Kaili Biota, nomen novum

Introduction

Zhao et al. (2010) proposed new edrioasteroid grade echinoderm genus *Kailidiscus* Zhao, Sumrall, Parsley & Peng, 2010 with type species *Kailidiscus chinensis* Zhao, Sumrall, Parsley & Peng, 2010 from the Kaili Biota of the basal lower Middle Cambrian Kaili Formation from Guizhou Province, China.

However, the genus name *Kailidiscus* is preoccupied and was initially introduced by Wang (2006) for an early Middle Cambrian ichnofossil species *Kailidiscus taijiangensis* Wang, 2006, as the type species and another species *Kailidiscus triasterism* Wang, 2006, from the Kaili Biota, a Burgess Shale-type biota, from the middle Kaili Formation in Taijiang County, Guizhou Province, southern China. Thus, echinoderm genus *Kailidiscus* Zhao, Sumrall, Parsley & Peng, 2010 is a junior homonym of *Kailidiscus* Wang, 2006. Since no synonyms are available, according to Article 60 of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN, 1999), a replacement name is needed for *Kailidiscus* Zhao, Sumrall, Parsley & Peng, 2010.

Parsleya U.B.Deshmukh **new name**

= *Kailidiscus* Zhao, Sumrall, Parsley & Peng, 2010: 674 (a junior homonym of *Kailidiscus* Wang, 2006: 29)

Etymology. The generic name is dedicated to Professor Emeritus Ronald L. Parsley who is one of the authors of the preexisting generic name *Kailidiscus*. The gender is feminine.

Parsleya chinensis (Zhao, Sumrall, Parsley & Peng, 2010), **new combination**
= *Kailidiscus chinensis* Zhao, Sumrall, Parsley & Peng, 2010: 675

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References

- ICZN [International Commission of Zoological Nomenclature] 1999 International Code of Zoological Nomenclature. Fourth edition, adopted by the International Union of Biological Sciences. International Trust for Zoological Nomenclature, c/o The Natural History Museum, London, xxx + 306 pp.
- Wang Y. 2006 A New Ichnogenus *Kailidiscus* Produced by Attachment from the Middle Cambrian Kaili Formation in Taijiang, Guizhou Province, China. *Acta Geologica Sinica* 80 (1): 27–37.
- Zhao Y., Sumrall C.D., Parsley R.D., Peng J. 2010 *Kailidiscus*, a new plesiomorphic edrioasteroid from the Kaili biota of Guizhou Province, China. *Journal of Paleontology* 84 (4): 668–680.
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